

PRISMA 2020 Flow Diagram (Textual Representation)

Identification:

Records identified from databases (Google Scholar via Publish or Perish): n = 475

Records removed before screening:

- Duplicate records removed: n = 125

- Records removed for other reasons: n = 50

Screening:

Records screened: n = 300

Records excluded: n = 160

Eligibility:

Reports sought for retrieval: n = 140

Reports not retrieved: n = 100

Reports assessed for eligibility: n = 40

Reports excluded: n = 0

Included:

Studies included in systematic and bibliometric review: n = 40